
Motivational Incentives and Teachers' Job Performance: Exploring the Influence of Gender, Location, and Experience in Lagos State Schools

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Abstract

This study investigated "Appraisal of Teachers' Perception of Motivational Activities and Its Influence on Their Job Performance: A Case Study of Lagos State Schools. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. Literature review was carried out in areas pertinent to the study. The design of the study was a descriptive survey. Out of a population of 3,114 senior secondary school teachers, 612 of them drawn by simple random and stratified random sampling techniques constituted the sample of the study. Data for the study were collected using a questionnaire titled "Motivational Incentives and Teachers' Job Performance (MITJP)". The instrument was developed and validated by the researcher, while the reliability of the instrument was determined by test-retest and Pearson's product-moment correlation technique, with a reliability coefficient of 0.80. The result of the data was analyzed using percentages. Results of the study indicated that the motivational items surrounding monetary incentives, welfare activities, and provision and availability of adequate instructional materials are all strong motivational factors that influence teachers' job performance. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that the Post Primary Schools Services, Lagos State, under whose auspices the motivation of secondary school teachers lies, should promote fairness and inclusivity in the distribution of incentives and opportunities, irrespective of gender, location, or experience. Equal managerial roles should be assigned irrespective of gender, and adequate support is provided to both new and experienced teachers across all regions to sustain motivation and enhance job performance.

Keywords: Motivational incentives, Teachers' job performance, Gender influence, Location impact, Teaching experience, Lagos State schools

1.0 Introduction

Authorities and institutions may build and equip schools with the basic science and technical equipment, provide all the basic educational materials, renovate and rehabilitate all old schools, provide library and other necessary facilities as well as employ the best qualified staff, yet the problem confronting educational administration would be half solved if the teachers who are the bedrock of education are not motivated.

The education sector has experienced a radical paradigm shift in Nigeria and the world at large. Governments, curriculum planners, parents, and the students themselves are concerned with the quality-of-service delivery from our teachers. Education has the purpose of catalysing the transformation of society for its development. It involves the art and act in which people are prepared to create new working habits and values for their changing lives in a dynamic environment (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization UNESCO, 2004). Among other functions, education increases the productivity of societies and attendant political, economic, and social institutions. (Puja, 2018).

Education is a major concern of human societies. It transcends the mere acquisition of knowledge and skills, hence the development of an individual who is transformed with the ability to understand and manipulate this world (Otunga, Odeo & Barasa, 2011). This conceptualization premises that the child is exposed to three dimensions to help them acquire education: formal dimension, known to be planned, organized, and systematic, often associated with institutions such as schools. The second one is an informal dimension entrenched as a lifelong process with attendant agents of socialization, including the mass media, peer groups, and religious institutions. Thirdly, the non-formal dimension is a framework of learning outside the school, though organized and planned. It is these dimensions that help the child to acquire knowledge and skills, develop reasoning in social relations, cultivate social virtues, and shape the child's habits, traits, and attitude. (Puja, 2018). High-quality education is emphasized as the key tool for the development of young citizens with the competences they need to adapt to a globalized society.

However, the success and failure in achieving quality education lie primarily with teachers. Teachers play a vital role in ensuring high-quality education. Nyakundi (2012) explains that teacher motivation is the most important factor in the promotion of teaching and learning excellence. He further adds, motivated teachers are more likely to motivate students to learn and to ensure the implementation of education reform. Therefore, the quality of an educational system cannot outperform the quality of its teacher (Federal Ministry of Education FME, 2007).

A survey conducted recently on teachers' motivation and job satisfaction in 12 countries in Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria, raises concerns about the low motivation among the teachers, which has led to teacher absenteeism, lateness, and lack of commitment to their work (Bennell & Akyeampong, 2007). Other studies have investigated variables of motivation such as working environment, management leadership style, incentives to employees, and participation in decision-making.

Several researchers, for their studies, have developed a working definition for teacher motivation and job satisfaction. Richardson (2014) defines teacher motivation as the internal and external factors that stimulate desire or energy in teaching to be continuously interested and committed to making their best effort to support students' learning goals. Whereas Guajardo (2011) describes motivation as the willingness, drive, or desire to engage in good teaching. Broussard and Garrison (2004) broadly define motivation as "the attribute that

moves us to do or not to do something”. Motivation is the driving force by which humans achieve their goals. Unless and until the employees are motivated and satisfied, an organization cannot foster success.

Staff motivation, therefore, has to do with how staff members perceive their work and how much they are committed to their work. Not all employees share the same motivational drive; therefore, understanding each employee’s needs and assisting them to reach their satisfied drivers is also a way of motivating them (Lipman, 2014). There seem to be some motivational factors that influence the job performance of teachers better than others.

Job performance is defined as the total expected value to the organization of the discrete behavioural episodes that an individual carries out over a standard period. Performance refers only to behaviours that can make a difference to organizational goal accomplishment. Employee motivation has a strong influence on the effectiveness of an organization (Paul, 2017).

The need for this study arose out of the researcher's concern for the need to redress the sagging morale of teachers resulting from inadequate attention paid to their welfare (Richardson, 2014). Nbina (2012) opined that teachers of today are buffered by many challenges which dampen their moral and lower their motivation to perform effectively and this could have an adverse effect on the educational system.

Research Questions

1. How does a teacher’s gender influence his/her perception of motivational activities on job performance?
2. To what extent does teachers’ location influence their perception of motivational activities on job performance?
3. Do teachers’ experiences on the job influence their perception of motivational activities on job performance?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the gender of teachers and their perception of motivational activities as it affects their job performance.
2. The location of teachers does not affect their perception of motivational activities on job performance.
3. Teachers’ experience on the job does not influence their perception of motivational activities.

2.0 Literature Review

Motivation is a general term applying to the entire class of drives, desires, needs, wishes, and similar forces. While teacher motivation is fundamental to the teaching and learning process, research studies show that many teachers in developing countries are not highly motivated. According to Michaelowa (2002), several factors negatively influence teacher motivation and job satisfaction in developing countries. This should be taken seriously, and an investigation into teachers’ motivation and job satisfaction is therefore necessary to achieve the educational goals. Motivation refers to “the reasons behind underlying behavior” (Guay et al. 2010).

Sharifand Nazir (2016) ascertain that different components and factors affecting employees’ job satisfaction, including and found working environment, pay and promotion, job security, and level of fairness, have significant relationships with job satisfaction. They further extend that low job satisfaction of the employees leads to a lack of productivity, job stress, poor overall performance, and employee turnover rate. They suggest that by giving good salaries

and promotion opportunities, the performance of the organization, service quality, and job satisfaction among employees can be increased.

Furthermore, Nyakundi (2012) defines job satisfaction as the feeling by the employee towards the job they do regarding conditions of work and the rewards accrued. Employees' satisfaction with their jobs is essential for the company, which will prevent bad performance and huge losses. Providing and stimulating employees' growth motivation is an essential method of increasing the level of motivation. (Lipman, 2014). Several studies found that teacher motivation and job satisfaction play vital roles in the success of the teaching and learning process.

According to Ololube (2005), teacher motivation and job satisfaction are not only crucial to the long-term growth of any educational system but also very essential in the lives of teachers as they form the fundamental reason for working. Nyakundi (2012) also indicates that teacher motivation is an important factor for classroom effectiveness and school improvement. He argues that high levels of job dissatisfaction, stress, and burnout negatively influence motivation and job performance. A lot of research has pointed out that teachers suffer from higher levels of professional stress and lower levels of motivation than other professional groups (De Jesus & Lens, 2005).

In the absence of motivation, is demotivation. Ushioda (2011) also suggested five categories of demotivating factors, including stress, inhibition of teacher autonomy, insufficient self-efficacy, inadequate career structures, content repetitiveness and limited potential for intellectual development.

Job performance is related to the extent to which an employee can accomplish the task assigned to him or her and how the accomplished task contributes to the realization of the organizational goal (Mawoli & Babandako, 2011)

Campbell (1990) and his associates (Campbell et al., 1996; Campbell, McCloy, Oppler, & Sager, 1993) presented a theory of performance that formalized relations found by Borman et al. (1991) between ability, job knowledge, skill, and job performance. They argued that there are three direct determinants of job performance: declarative knowledge, procedural knowledge and skill, and motivation.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory (Maslow, 1954) has been a very popular motivation theory and can be applied in every organization. The theory saw human needs in the form of a hierarchy, ascending from the lowest to the highest, and he concluded that when one set of needs is satisfied, this kind of need ceases to be a motivation. He therefore placed the basic human needs in an ascending order of importance as follows: physical needs, safety needs, social needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization. Abraham Maslow's theory argues that humans have a series of needs, some of which must be met before they can turn their attention toward others. (Horne, 2019). The goal of Maslow's theory is to attain the highest level of stage: self-actualization needs" (McEwen & Wills, 2014). If this level is deficient, an individual's all behaviours will be directed to content the deficits. (Cherry, 2015).

Appraisal of the Reviewed Literature

Yemisi (2013) revealed that no significant difference was found in the motivation of male and female, untrained and trained, experienced and inexperienced teachers. Gehlawat et al. (2013) I his study found no significant difference in the job satisfaction and work motivation of male and female teachers. He also revealed that there were significant differences among teachers working in government and private schools; more experienced and less experienced teachers concerning job satisfaction and work motivation, and that significant difference was reported

in the work motivation of teachers having graduate and post-graduate qualifications. Saeed and Muneer (2012) found that female teachers were found to be more motivated by their work than male teachers. Khan (2001) found that significantly different teachers at government senior secondary schools in general possessed work motivation to some extent, and no significant difference was found in the overall work motivation of the male and female teachers. Saeed and Muneer (2012) revealed that female teachers were found to be more motivated by their work than male teachers.

Duru (1992) found no significant difference between the responses of experienced and inexperienced teachers on the factors responsible for the teacher's poor performance in their work. The result of his study also revealed that the male teachers were significantly influenced negatively by the non-provision of incentives to teachers more than the female teachers. Ogbu (1981) also, in a related study, found that there was no significant difference between the perception of urban and rural teachers, as well as experienced and inexperienced teachers' work motivation.

3.0 Methodology

The design of the study is a descriptive survey. All the senior secondary school teachers in the Education District V in Lagos State constituted the population of this study. The teachers were 3,114 in 2020 when this study was conducted. The district is made up of four education zones, namely: Ajeromi/Ifelodun, Amuwo Odofin, Badagry and Ojo. Information obtained from Post Primary School Service Commission (PPSSC) Headquarters Ikeja revealed that out of the 139 senior secondary schools in the district, there are 39, 40, 28 and 32 in Ajeromi/Ifelodun, Amuwo Odofin, Badagry and Ojo zones respectively.

A combination of simple random sampling and stratified random sampling was used for this study. A total of 28 senior secondary schools (7 in each zone), selected through a simple random sampling technique, were used for the study. This means that the sample consisted of 20% of the teachers in each of the four zones in Education District V.

The sample of this study consisted of 612 senior secondary school teachers, drawn by a stratified random sampling technique. The stratification was in line with the teachers' gender, location, and level of experience. The gender consists of male and female. The location strata include urban and rural areas. The urban and rural areas were chosen in line with the Lagos State standard. The rural area by this standard is Badagry Local Government Area in Education District V, where the study was conducted, while the other three local government areas/zones, Ajeromi/Ifelodun, Amuwo Odofin, and Ojo, are classified as urban areas. Furthermore, experienced teachers referred to teachers who have spent 3 years and above on the job while teachers who have spent below 3 years are said to be 'new on the job'.

Details of the stratified sample population in percentage are as follows: Male teachers: 42%, Female teachers: 58%, Experienced teachers: 68%, Inexperienced teachers: 32%, Urban area teachers: 68%, Rural area teachers: 32%.

Data for the study were collected using a questionnaire titled "Motivational Incentives and Teachers' Job Performance (MITJP)". (This is found in Appendix A). An initial pool of 30 items (15 items in section A and 15 items in section B) that constituted draft of the instruments were sent to two specialists in Educational Measurement and Administration and two secondary school teachers to vet the instrument in terms of the clarity of words and suitability of the listed items in enhancing the senior secondary school teachers' job performance. The reliability coefficient of the instrument (MITJP) was determined using test-re-test method using 10 teachers. The scores were correlated using the Pearson product

moment correlation technique. A reliability coefficient of 0.80 was obtained for the instrument. The value was considered high enough and thus adequate for the study. The computation was shown in Appendix B. Although 623 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, only 612, representing 98%, were returned and used in data analysis.

Discussion of findings:

Research Question 1: How does teachers’ gender influence his/her perception of motivational activities on job performance?

Table 1: Gender and Motivation.(M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation.)

S/N	Items	Responses	Percentage(%)		Male		Female	
			Male	Female	M	SD	M	SD
1.	Teachers’ salaries are paid promptly and not owed.	High degree Low degree	100 0	100 0	4.00	0.22	4.00	0.22
2.	Promoting teachers when they are due.	High degree Low degree	99 1	99 1	3.98	0.25	3.98	0.25
3.	Allowing teachers to have professional autonomy and authority to use their discretion and make minor classroom decisions.	High degree Low degree	97 3	97 3	3.96	0.10	3.86	0.20
4.	The availability of the staff bus.	High degree Low degree	89 11	98 2	3.82	0.48	3.90	0.60
5.	Rewarding or recognizing teachers who have performed excellently.	High degree Low degree	93 7	97 3	3.87	0.50	3.90	0.70
6.	Providing conducive staff quarters.	High degree Low degree	93 7	97 3	3.92	0.80	3.88	0.95
7.	Helping staff have access to mortgage loans and other loans, like car loans and medical loans.	High degree Low degree	93 7	98 2	3.93	0.49	3.94	0.51
8.	Retired teachers are receiving their gratuities and pensions promptly.	High degree Low degree	98 2	92 8	3.98	0.40	3.82	0.39
9.	Provision of relevant textbooks, journals, magazines, and instructional materials.	High degree Low degree	89 11	94 6	3.83	0.70	3.84	0.40
10	Classroom and school renovations to ensure it’s conducive for learning.	High degree Low degree	90 10	98 2	3.83	0.40	3.94	0.39
	Average	High degree Low degree	94 6	97 3	3.91	0.45	3.86	0.47

Table 1 above shows that all the male and female teachers to the same degree perceive that prompt payment of salaries and teachers’ promotion as at when due at a very high degree influences their job performance at 100% and 99% respectively. The above table further reveals that both male and female teachers at 97% perceived at the same degree professional autonomy and authority as motivating. 89% of the male teachers perceived availability of staff bus as capable of motivating and influencing their job performance while the female

teachers stood at 98%. The male teachers at 93% perceived teachers' reward and recognition, provision of conducive staff quarters and access to mortgage and car loan to be motivating and influential to their job performance while the female teachers perceived same at 97%, 97% and 98% respectively. Item 8 to 10 responses also reveal very insignificant difference in the perception of both male and female teachers on motivation. The average percentage of the responses shows the male teachers' perception at 94% high degree and 6% low degree while the female teachers' perception stood at 97% high degree and 3% low degree. This exposes that these items were perceived by male and female teachers as being capable of enhancing their job performance.

The results indicate very insignificant or no difference in the perception of male and female teachers on motivation. This is evidenced in the average mean rating score of 3.91 for the male teachers and 3.86 for the female teachers with a standard deviation average of 0.45 for male teachers and 0.47 for female teachers. Since all the mean ratings are greater than the cut-off points of 2.50, it means that these items are perceived by male and female teachers alike as being capable of enhancing their job performance.

Research Question 2: To what extent does teachers' location influence their perception of motivational activities on job performance?

Table 2: Location and Motivation. (M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation.)

S/N	Items	Responses	Percentages		Urban		Rural	
			Urban	Rural	M	SD	M	SD
1.	Teachers' salaries are paid promptly and not owed.	High degree Low degree	100 0	100 0	4.00	0.57	4.00	0.56
2.	Promoting teachers when they are due.	High degree Low degree	99 1	99 1	3.98	0.53	4.00	0.56
3.	Allowing teachers to have professional autonomy and authority to use their discretion and make minor classroom decisions.	High degree Low degree	98 2	97 3	3.91	0.37	3.90	0.36
4.	The availability of the staff bus.	High degree Low degree	98 2	93 7	3.89	0.36	3.83	0.32
5.	Rewarding or recognizing teachers who have performed excellently.	High degree Low degree	97 3	94 6	3.90	0.40	3.86	0.60
6.	Providing conducive staff quarters.	High degree Low degree	98 2	98 2	3.90	0.58	3.91	0.50
7.	Helping staff have access to mortgage loans and other loans, like car loans and medical loans.	High degree Low degree	100 0	96 4	3.96	0.74	3.89	0.41
8.	Retired teachers are receiving their gratuities and pensions promptly.	High degree Low degree	95 5	98 2	3.88	0.40	3.94	0.30
9.	Provision of relevant textbooks, journals, magazines, and instructional materials.	High degree Low degree	94 6	94 6	3.83	0.29	3.85	0.30

10	Classroom and school renovations to ensure it's conducive for learning.	High degree	96	98	3.87	0.50	3.93	0.33
		Low degree	4	2				
	Average	High degree	97	98	3.91	0.40	3.85	0.42
		Low degree	3	2				

Table 2 above shows that the teachers located in urban and rural areas perceive prompt payment of salaries as highly motivating, with high influence on their job performance alike at 100%. It further shows that at 99%, the urban and rural teachers at the same degree found promotion of teachers as when due, motivating and influential as well. The above table further reveals that urban teacher at 98% and the rural teachers at 97% perceived professional autonomy and authority as highly motivating and influential on their job performance. Availability of staff bus was perceived to be motivating by urban teachers at 98%, more than rural teachers at 93%. This may be associated with difficulty commuting in an urban area with a denser population and high cost of transportation as well. Item 5 and 6 responses also reveal very insignificant or no difference in the perception of both urban and rural teachers on motivation. All the urban teachers at 100% degree perceived easy access to mortgage and car loans as highly motivating, with 96% of the rural teachers perceiving it as motivating as well. This may be connected to the high cost of renting apartments in the urban areas of Lagos State.

The average percentage of the responses shows the urban teachers' perception at 97% high degree and 3% low degree, while the rural teachers' perception stood at 98% high degree and 2% low degree, yet a very insignificant difference. This exposes that these items are perceived by urban and rural teachers as being capable of enhancing their job performance.

The above results also show very insignificant or no difference in the perception of urban and rural teachers on motivation. This is evidenced in the average mean rating score of 3.91 for the urban teachers and 3.85 for the rural teachers, with a standard deviation average of 0.40 for urban teachers and 0.42 for rural teachers. Since all the mean ratings are greater than the cut-off points of 2.50, it means that these items are perceived by urban and rural teachers as being capable of motivating them and enhancing their job performance, irrespective of their school location.

The result of the study shows that school location, urban or rural, is not a significant factor in influencing the teachers' perception of the effect of some motivational incentives on their job performance.

Research Question 3: Do teachers' experience on the job influence their perception of motivational activities on job performance?

Table 3: Experience and Motivation.(M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation.)

S/N	Items	Responses	Percentages		Experienced		New on the job	
			Experienced	New on the job	M	SD	M	SD
1.	Teachers' salaries paid promptly and not owed.	High degree Low degree	100 0	100 0	4.00	0.29	4.00	0.29
2.	Promoting teachers when they are due.	High degree Low degree	100 0	95 5	4.00	0.28	3.91	0.25
3.	Allowing teachers have professional autonomy and authority to use their discretion and take minor classroom decisions.	High degree Low degree	94 6	93 7	3.92	0.36	3.89	0.30
4.	The availability of staff bus.	High degree Low degree	88 12	95 5	3.82	0.29	3.93	0.38
5.	Rewarding or recognizing teachers who have performed excellently.	High degree Low degree	94 6	91 9	3.90	0.49	3.86	0.33
6.	Providing conducive staff quarters.	High degree Low degree	92 8	92 8	3.90	0.44	3.90	0.38
7.	Helping staff have access to mortgage loans and other loans like car loans and medical loan.	High degree Low degree	95 5	95 5	3.94	0.54	3.93	0.44
8.	Retired teachers receive their gratuities and pensions promptly.	High degree Low degree	96 4	88 12	3.94	0.50	3.78	0.35
9.	Provision of relevant textbooks, journals, magazines and instructional materials.	High degree Low degree	89 11	92 8	3.81	0.30	3.89	0.40
10	Classroom and school renovations to ensure it's conducive for learning.	High degree Low degree	93 7	93 7	3.88	0.40	3.90	0.56
	Average	High degree Low degree	94 6	94 6	3.91	0.38	3.86	0.40

Table 3 above reveals that both experienced teachers and teachers who are new on the job at the same degree of 100% perceived prompt payment of salaries as motivating and with high influence on their job performance. More so, the result in the table above shows very insignificant variation in the responses of both experienced and teachers who are new on the job in teachers' promotion, which at 100% and 95% was perceived as motivating irrespective of their level of experience.

Furthermore, 94% of experienced teachers perceived teachers' professional autonomy as a motivational item with high influence on their job performance, while 93% of teachers who are new on the job perceived it also to have a high influence on their job performance. 88% of experienced teachers and 95% of new teachers perceived the availability of a staff bus as motivating and capable of influencing their job performance. At 94 and 91% degrees, reward

and recognition of excellent with no significant difference was perceived as a motivating factor with high influence on both experienced and new teachers' job performance, as well as provision of conducive staff quarters and access to mortgage and car loan which at the same degree of perception for both experienced and new teachers stood at 92% and 95% respectively.

Items 8 to 10 responses also reveal very insignificant or no difference in the perception of both experienced and teachers who are new on the job on the influence of the motivational items on their job performance. The average percentage of the responses shows that the experienced teachers' perception was at 94% high degree and 6% low degree, while the new on-the-job teachers' perception stood at 94% high degree and 6% low degree. This exposes that these items were perceived by both experienced and new on-the-job teachers as being capable of enhancing their job performance.

The results also reveal very insignificant or no difference in the perception of experienced and teachers who are new on job on motivation and the influence it has on their job performance. This is corroborated in the average mean rating score of 3.91 for the experienced teachers and 3.86 for the new on the job teachers with a standard deviation average of 0.38 for experienced teachers and 0.40 for teachers who are new on the job. Since all the mean ratings are greater than the cut-off points of 2.50, it means that these items are perceived by urban and rural teachers as being capable of motivating them and enhancing their job performance irrespective of their level of experience.

The result of this study shows that no significant difference exists between the perception of experienced and new on-the-job teachers on the influence of motivational incentives on their job performance. That is, the item to the same extent influences their job performance.

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the gender of teachers in their perception of motivational activities as it affects their job performance.

Table 4: T-Test Comparison of the Mean of the Perception of Male and Female Teachers on the Influence of Motivational Incentives on their Job Performance. (X-Mean, SD-Standard Deviation, N – Sample Population, DF-Degree of Freedom, T-Cal-T-Test Calculated, T-Crit-T-Test Critical.)

Gender	X	SD	N	DF	T-Cal	T-Crit
Male	3.91	0.45	257	610	1.25	1.96
Female	3.86	0.47	355			

From table 4 above, the calculated values (t-cal) for teacher's gender is 1.25. The critical value (t-crit), at 0.05 level of significance and 610 degrees of freedom is 1.96. Since the calculated values of 1.25 is less than the critical value of 1.96, the first hypothesis is therefore accepted. This means that gender is not a significant factor on the perception of teachers with respect to the influence of motivational factors in enhancing teachers' job performance.

Hypothesis 2: Location of teachers do not affect their perception of motivational activities to job performance.

Table 5: T-Test Comparison of the Mean of the Perception of Urban and Rural Teachers on the Influence of Motivational Incentives on their Job Performance.

(X-Mean, SD-Standard Deviation, N – Sample Population, DF-Degree of Freedom, T-Cal-T-Test Calculated, T-Crit-T-Test Critical.)

School Location	X	SD	N	DF	T-Cal	T-Crit
Urban	3.91	0.40	420	610	1.50	1.96
Rural	3.85	0.42	192			

Table 5 above indicates that the calculated values of (t-cal) for-teacher’s location is 1.50. The critical value of (t-crit) at 0.05 level of significance and 610 degrees of freedom is 1.96. Since the calculated value is less than the critical value of 1.96, it means that the second null hypothesis is accepted. This means that the influence of motivational factors on teachers’ job performance is perceived as exerting the same effect on both urban and rural schools.

Hypothesis 3: Teachers’ experience on the job does not influence their perception of motivational activities.

Table 6: T- Test Comparison of the Mean of the Perception of Experienced and Teachers who are new on the Job on the Influence of Motivational Incentives on their Job Performance.

(X-Mean, SD-Standard Deviation, N – Sample Population, DF-Degree of Freedom, T-Cal-T-Test Calculated, T-Crit-T-Test Critical.)

Work Experience	X	SD	N	DF	T-Cal	T-Crit
Experienced	3.91	0.38	413	610	1.25	1.96
Inexperienced	3.86	0.40	199			

Table 6 above shows the calculated values of (t-cal) for the influence of motivational factors as perceived by experienced and newly recruited teachers, as 1.25. The critical value of t (t-crit) at 0.05 level of significance and 610 degrees of freedom is 1.96. Since the t-calculated is less than the critical value, it means that the third null hypothesis is accepted as stated.

5.0 Conclusion

The findings of the study reveal that gender was not a significant factor in the influence of some motivational incentives on teachers' job performance, since all the item means for both male and female teachers were greater than the cut-off point of 2.50 and the t-calculated of 1.25 was also less than the t-critical value of 1.96 irrespective of the gender. Thus, no significant difference was observed between the mean ratings of the male and female teachers. Although both male and female teachers had positive views on the impact of

motivational incentives on their job performance, male teachers showed a more enthusiastic view on the need for the provision of such incentives, although the difference between their views was not significant. This is supported by studies on gender differences in perception of motivation by Yemisi (2013) and Gehlawat, et al. (2013), which did not find any significant difference between the perception of males and females on the influence of motivational factors on their job performance. This implies that employees in a workplace have the same level of motivation in the workplace regardless of their gender. Thus, when it comes to assigning responsibilities, human resources should consider such findings and assign employees responsibilities without discrimination. Teachers must be treated fairly, especially when it comes to the administrative tasks, promotion, and giving an equal chance for leadership, responsibilities.

Similarly, result of the study shows that school location, urban or rural, was not a significant factor in influencing the teachers' perception of the effect of some motivational incentives on their job performance. This is evidenced by the means for both urban and rural teachers, which surpassed the cut-off point of 2.50 and the t-calculated of 0.75, which was also less than the t-critical value of 1.96, irrespective of their location. The result of this study was in harmony with Okwo (1990) and Ogbu (1981), who reported that there was no significant difference between urban and rural teachers on their views of teachers' job performance level. The reason for this non-difference on the influence of motivators/ incentives on teachers' job performance could be attributed to the fact that teachers everywhere had similar basic needs, which include that of satisfying their personal needs: food, shelter, clothing, medicare, etc. Thus, teachers in both urban and rural secondary schools in Education District V in Lagos State equally demand the provision of some incentives to enhance their job performance.

Furthermore, result of this study also reveals that no significant difference existed between the mean perception of experienced teachers and those who are new to the job on the influence of motivational incentives on their job performance. The means of both experienced and inexperienced teachers exceeded the cut-off point of 2.80, and the t-calculated of 1.25 was less than the t-critical of 1.96. Thus, no difference existed between the perception of experienced and inexperienced teachers on the influence of some motivational incentives on job performance. A study by Yemisi (2013) supports this result, where she found that there was no significant difference in the perception of experienced and inexperienced teachers on motivation. Duru (1992) in a similar study revealed that no significant difference between the responses of experienced and inexperienced teachers on the factors responsible for the teacher's poor performance in their work. This clearly showed that the item to the same extent influences their job performance. An explanation of this observation could be deduced from the point of view of Iliya and Ifeoma (2015) where they indicated that both experienced and inexperienced teachers were old enough to determine what they like or dislike as well as what they expect that would enhance the performance of that job. Indeed, beyond the childhood stage, individuals are expected to be reasonable enough to decide what they want or otherwise. This decision-making is usually based on some established criteria. Thus, teachers whether experienced or not have all outgrown childhood stage and as such can make precise demands as regards those incentives that would enhance their job performance.

6.0 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this work the same recommendations were made. The Post Primary Schools Services, Lagos State under whose auspices the motivation of secondary school teachers lies should ensure that:

- There should be equal treatment and incentive distribution among teachers of all genders, locations, experiences, and levels.

- Seminars, workshops, conferences, and symposia are organized regularly for teachers to keep abreast with the innovative skills/strategies in their subject areas.
- Autonomy is given to all teachers, with no reference to teachers' gender, status or location. Male and female teachers should be given equal opportunities and equal rewards. Incentives should not be gender based, and women should not be discriminated against when assigning managerial functions or when it involves incentives like travelling, international trainings, and conferences.
- Teachers in rural areas should not be relegated for any reason. Teachers in urban and rural areas should be rewarded and given opportunities alike. The provision of instructional materials should reach both rural and urban areas.
- Incentives are given to teachers without favoritism of any sort.
- Equal managerial opportunities should be given to both male and female teachers.
- Teachers who are new on the job should be encouraged and motivated adequately, provided with adequate instructional materials, periodic training, and follow-up to ensure their progress and identify areas of concern to ensure that demotivation does not occur.

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APPENDIX A

MOTIVATIONAL INCENTIVES AND TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE (MITJP)

Section A: Personal Data

Please provide the following information about you. A tick () may be used where necessary.

1. **Name of School**.....
2. **Gender:** Male () Female ()
3. **Work Experience:** Below 3 years (); 3 years and above ().

Section B: Perception of Motivational Incentives to Teachers.

Read the underlined statement and use a tick () to respond accordingly.

- Note:** HD = High Degree
 AD = Average Degree
 LD = Low Degree
 ND = No Degree

Kindly indicate the degree to which the following incentives would influence your job performance.

S/N	Items	HD	AD	LD	ND
1.	Prompt payment and periodic increment of salaries.				
2.	Teachers promotion as at when due.				
3.	Teachers professional autonomy and authority.				
4.	Provision of staff bus.				
5.	Reward/recognition of excellent performers				
6.	Provision of conducive staff quarters.				
7.	Granting access to mortgage and car loans.				
8.	Prompt payment of gratuities and pensions.				
9.	Provision of relevant textbooks, journals, magazines and instructional materials.				
10.	Provision conducive classroom and school environment.				

APPENDIX B

**DETERMINATION OF THE RELIABILITY OF THE INSTRUMENT (MITJP)
 USING THE PEARSON MOMENT CORRELATION TECHNIQUE.**

Formula:
$$R = \frac{N\sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{(N\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2)(N\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2)}}$$

Where: R= Pearson product moment correlation coefficient.
 XZY = Two sets of scores obtained from the same group of subjects during test.
 Σ = Sum of; N= Number of subjects.

S/NO	X	Y	X'	Y ²	XY
1	57	55	3249	3025	3135
2	66	60	4356	3600	3960
3	60	52	3600	2704	3120
4	51	48	2601	2304	2448
5	80	72	6400	5184	5760
6	54	48	2916	2304	2592
7	63	54	3969	2916	3402
8	57	64	3249 -	4096	3648
9	60	50	3600	2500	3000
10	69	64	4761	4096	4416
11	43	54	1849	2916	2322
12	37	28	1369	784	1036
13	60	55	3600	3025	3300
14	66	70	4356	4900	4620
15	57	44	3249	3025	3125
16	54	54	2916	2916	2916

17	63	65	3969	4225	4095
18	51	53	2601	2809	2703
19	74	80	5476	6400	5020
20	49	47	2401	2209	2303
Total	1748	1739	104486	104665	103882

Substituting in the above formula:

$$\frac{20 \times 103882 - 1748 \times 1739}{\sqrt{(20 \times 104486) - (1748)^2 (20 \times 104665 - 1739)^2}}$$

$$\frac{76688}{(79076)(115829)} = \frac{76688}{95704.2} = 0.81$$

APPENDIX C
COMPUTATION OF MEANS AND STANDARD DEVIATION FOR THE PERCEPTION OF MALE AND FEMALE TEACHERS ON THE DEGREE OF THE INFLUENCE OF MOTIVATION ON THEIR JOB PERFORMANCE.

Note: (HD-High Degree, AD-Average Degree, LD-Low Degree, ND-No Degree, N-Number, X-Mean, SD-Standard Deviation.)

Male Teachers

S/N	HD	AD	LD	ND	N	X	SD
1	257	0	0	0	257	4.00	0.22
2	254	0	3	0	257	3.98	0.25
3	249	6	2	0	257	3.96	0.10
4	230	12	12	3	257	3.82	0.48
5	240	4	10	3	257	3.87	0.50
6	239	15	3	0	257	3.92	0.80
7	240	17	0	0	257	3.93	0.49
8	251	6	0	0	257	3.98	0.40
9	230	12	13	2	257	3.83	0.70
10	231	11	12	3	257	3.83	0.40

Average **3.91** **0.47**

Female Teachers

S/N	HD	AD	LD	ND	N	X	SD
1	355	0	0	0	355	4.00	0.22
2	351	0	4	0	355	3.98	0.25
3	324	20	7	4	355	3.86	0.20
4	327	21	7	0	355	3.90	0.60
5	330	14	11	0	355	3.90	0.70

6	325	19	11	0	355	3.88	0.95
7	341	7	7	0	355	3.94	0.51
8	320	7	28	0	355	3.82	0.39
9	320	14	21	0	355	3.84	0.40
10	339	9	7	0	355	3.94	0.39

Average

3.91 0.47

APPENDIX D
COMPUTATION OF MEANS AND STANDARD DEVIATION FOR THE PERCEPTION OF URBAN AND RURAL TEACHERS ON THE DEGREE OF THE INFLUENCE OF MOTIVATION ON THEIR JOB PERFORMANCE.

Note: (HD-High Degree, AD-Average Degree, LD-Low Degree, ND-No Degree, N-Number, X-Mean, SD-Standard Deviation.)

Urban Teachers

S/N	HD	AD	LD	ND	N	X	SD
1	420	0	0	0	420	4.00	0.57
2	415	0	5	0	420	3.98	0.53
3	394	18	6	2	420	3.91	0.37
4	382	29	9	0	420	3.89	0.36
5	393	14	10	3	420	3.90	0.40
6	386	24	10	0	420	3.90	0.58
7	403	17	0	0	420	3.96	0.74
8	390	10	20	0	420	3.88	0.40
9	374	22	22	2	420	3.83	0.29
10	387	15	15	3	420	3.87	0.50

Average **3.91** **0.42**

Rural Teachers

S/N	HD	AD	LD	ND	N	X	SD
1	192	0	0	0	192	4.00	0.56
2	190	0	2	0	192	4.00	0.56
3	179	8	3	2	192	3.90	0.36
4	175	4	10	3	192	3.83	0.32
5	177	4	11	0	192	3.86	0.60

6	178	10	4	0	192	3.91	0.50
7	178	7	7	0	192	3.89	0.41
8	185	3	4	0	192	3.94	0.30
9	176	4	12	0	192	3.85	0.30
10	183	5	4	0	192	3.93	0.33

Average

3.91 0.42

APPENDIX E
COMPUTATION OF MEANS AND STANDARD DEVIATION FOR THE PERCEPTION OF EXPERIENCED AND NEW TEACHERS ON THE DEGREE OF THE INFLUENCE OF MOTIVATION ON THEIR JOB PERFORMANCE.

Note: (HD-High Degree, AD-Average Degree, LD-Low Degree, ND-No Degree, N-Number, X-Mean, SD-Standard Deviation.)

Experienced Teachers

S/N	HD	AD	LD	ND	N	X	SD
1	413	0	0	0	413	4.00	0.29
2	413	0	0	0	413	4.00	0.28
3	387	20	3	3	413	3.92	0.36
4	364	28	18	3	413	3.82	0.29
5	389	10	11	3	413	3.90	0.49
6	381	22	10	0	413	3.90	0.44
7	392	18	3	0	413	3.94	0.54
8	396	9	8	0	413	3.94	0.50
9	366	18	27	2	413	3.81	0.30
10	384	13	13	3	413	3.88	0.40
Average					3.91	0.39	

New Teachers

S/N	HD	AD	LD	ND	N	X	SD
1	199	0	0	0	199	4.00	0.29
2	189	3	7	0	199	3.91	0.25
3	186	6	6	0	199	3.89	0.30
4	190	5	4	0	199	3.93	0.38

5	181	8	10	0	199	3.86	0.33
6	183	12	4	0	199	3.90	0.38
7	189	6	4	0	199	3.93	0.44
8	175	4	20	0	199	3.78	0.35
9	184	8	7	0	199	3.89	0.40
10	186	7	6	0	199	3.90	0.56
Average					3.90	0.40	

APPENDIX F COMPUTATION OF T-TEST

Formula:

$$T_{X_1-X_2} = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{SD_1^2 + SD_2^2}{N_1 + N_2 - 2}}}$$

Where :

$\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2$ = means for group 1 and 2 respectively

$SD_1^2 + SD_2^2$ = S.D for group 1 and 2 respectively

$N_1 + N_2 - 2$ = degree of freedom

Hypothesis one:

$$\frac{3.91 - 3.86}{\sqrt{\frac{0.45^2}{257-1} + \frac{0.47^2}{355-1}}} = \frac{0.05}{\sqrt{0.001 + 0.001}}$$

$$= \frac{0.05}{0.04} = 1.25$$

Hypothesis Two:

$$\frac{3.91 - 3.85}{\sqrt{\frac{0.40^2}{420-1} + \frac{0.42^2}{192-1}}} = \frac{0.06}{\sqrt{0.001 + 0.001}}$$

$$= \frac{0.06}{0.04} = 1.50$$

Hypothesis Three:

$$\frac{3.91 - 3.86}{\sqrt{\frac{0.38^2}{413-1} + \frac{0.40^2}{199-1}}} = \frac{0.05}{\sqrt{0.001 + 0.001}}$$

$$= \frac{0.05}{0.04} = 1.25$$